

HORIZON JU Research and Innovation Actions
HORIZON-EUROHPC-JU-2021-COE-01-01
European High-Performance Computing Joint Undertaking

Plasma Exascale-Performance Simulations CoE
101093261

D1.9
**First Release – Plasma Simulation Codes and
Documentation**

WP1: Plasma Simulations - Codes and Grand Challenges

Date of preparation (latest version): 31/12/2024
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DOCUMENT INFORMATION

Deliverable Number	D1.9
Deliverable Name	First Release – Plasma Simulation Codes and Documentation
Due Date	31/12/2024
Deliverable lead	MPG
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Keywords	Software Release
WP/Task	WP1/Task D1.9
Nature	R
Dissemination Level	PU
Final Version Date	31/12/2024
Reviewed by	Leon Kos (UL) & Filippo Mantovani (BSC)

DOCUMENT HISTORY

Partner	Date	Comment	Version
KTH	03/03/2024	Skeleton version of the deliverable	0.1
MPG	07/11/20024	Skeleton adapted	0.2
MPG	02/12/2024	First draft	0.3
KTH	03/12/2024	Final draft updated for internal review	0.4
MPG	12/12/2024	Revised draft after internal review	0.5
KTH	20/12/2024	Final cleanup for submission	1.0

Executive Summary

In this deliverable, we publicly release current versions of the codes within the project and summarize the contributions to the codes made since the beginning of Plasma-PEPSC two years ago.

In short, BIT1 development was split into four parts: optimization (vectorization) of a number of functions, implementation of the parallel I/O via openPMD-API and ADIOS-2 libraries, load balancing and GPU porting. The first two tasks were (almost) completed, while the others are under development.

The development work for GENE and GENEX was mainly put into the GPU porting of the GENEX code, which will take most of the envisaged runtime of the target run. The code was fully ported with an OpenMP directives approach, and now the time loop completely runs on NVIDIA GPUs. The extension to AMD GPUs (like in LUMI-G) is in development.

The development of PIConGPU is focused on realizing the exascale science case, with proposals for LUMI and JUPITER currently under consideration. The project includes the implementation of a high-precision laser model and associated solvers, which are expected to reach completion by 2025. Full-scale simulation runs have already been planned to take advantage of these advances. To enhance the performance of PIConGPU, significant updates have been made to its parallelism infrastructure, which is based on the alpaka library, including improvements to vectorization support. The on-device memory allocation scheme has been updated using MallocMC. To address the I/O and analysis bottleneck, work was done to enable PIConGPU, integrated with openPMD, to function as part of an in situ machine learning (ML) workflow, and this was successfully demonstrated in a full-scale run. PIConGPU has also already demonstrated its scalability and capability through full-scale runs on LUMI this year.

Vlasiator’s development focussed on performance portability onto both vector-heavy and GPU-heavy target platforms, with a major restructuring of solver data structures and flow control behavior to be both flexible and future-proof. In parallel, algorithmic improvements of both the Vlasov and field solvers substantially improved the HPC scaling behavior of the code. New, more dynamic adaptive mesh refinement methods allow the simulations’ resolution to track areas of physical interest more effectively. New in situ data reducers for magnetic topology identification and non-Maxwellianity measures allow for reduced output file footprints. The adoption of more structured development practices and more end-user outreach has greatly improved documentation and usability.

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1 Introduction

The four codes of the project have been developed during the first two years of the project and the current versions are released with this deliverable. The main purpose is to make available the first public version for review. Some of the codes already had a regular release cycle with many predecessor public releases (Vlasiator, PIconGPU, GENE), and some codes are for the first time released into the public (GENEX and BIT). Together with the codes, user documentation has been published in the respective repositories.

2 Code Releases

All four codes have been released and can be accessed publicly or by reviewers on request.

2.1 BIT

BIT1 is released through its official main development repository at

<https://repo.tok.ipp.cas.cz/tskhakaya/bit1>

and mirrored to

<https://codehub.hlrs.de/coes/plasma-pepsc/ippcas/bit1>

under the customized license

<https://repo.tok.ipp.cas.cz/tskhakaya/bit1/-/wikis/home>

We decided to keep this strategy until the final version of the code is developed. The latest release is “BIT1-9”; the user manual can be found on the same site.

2.2 GENE/GENEX

GENE has been released with a customized Open Source license under the official URL,

<https://gitlab.mpcdf.mpg.de/GENE/gene.git>

which is accessible only to registered users. Registration is open to everyone and can be requested at www.genecode.org. The current release is in branch `release-3.1`. Release notes (file `CHANGELOG.md`) can be found in the code repository of the release with a summary on what progress the code made during the project, which is mainly related to AMD GPU and LUMI support. The repository is also mirrored to

<https://codehub.hlrs.de/coes/plasma-pepsc/mpg/gene.git>

GENEX has been released for the very first time under

<https://gitlab.mpcdf.mpg.de/phoenix-public/genex>

with the release tag 1.0.0. GENEX uses the ParallaX library, which in turn depends on the PAccX library for GPU simulations. In addition, both use ConfiX for common configuration tasks. All of these repositories are also released publicly under the same gitlab group `phoenix-public`. The access to the group will be granted on request (please send an email to dannert@mpcdf.mpg.de), and a full publication with an open source license will happen in 2025 in the EuroFusion context.

2.3 PICongGPU

PICongGPU is developed as an open-source project under the GPLv3+ license, with an open development model. The project is hosted at

<https://github.com/ComputationalRadiationPhysics/picongpu>

and mirrored to

<https://codehub.hlr.de/coes/plasma-pepsc/hzdr/picongpu>

We use public GitHub issues so that users and developers can report issues, suggest improvements, and participate in discussions. Similarly all contributions to the code are managed via public pull requests, enabling transparency and community engagement in the development process. All current and future releases are distributed under the GPLv3+ license, ensuring freedom to use, modify, and share the software. Regular releases are accompanied by changelogs, detailing new features, improvements, and bug fixes; these releases can be accessed at

<https://github.com/ComputationalRadiationPhysics/picongpu/releases>

The latest release is version 0.7.0. and the current state of development is always visible publicly in the "dev" branch. The next release, 0.8.0, is in the final stages of review, and will be released by mid-December 2024.

2.4 Vlasiator

Vlasiator is released through its official main development repository at

<https://github.com/fmihpc/vlasiator>

and mirrored to

<https://codehub.hlr.de/coes/plasma-pepsc/uoh/vlasiator>

under the GPL-2 open-source license. The most recent release version at the point of this document release is the tag `v5.3.1`. Future development and release versions will continue to be available from the same repository under an open-source license.

An unsupported pre-release of the GPU port of Vlasiator has been made available under the tag `GPU_v1` at the same repository.

3 Conclusion

All codes have been released with a well-defined version in a public or reviewer-accessible repository. Release notes with a description of the work on the codes during the first two years of the project have been added directly to the repositories in files called "RELEASE_NOTES.md" or similar in the respective base directory.